

EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON FOOD SECURITY STATUS OF RICE FARMING HOUSEHOLDS IN KEBBI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of climate change on the food security status of rice farming households in Kebbi State, Nigeria. One hundred and eighty households from Bunza, Zuru and Argungu local government areas were selected for the study by multi-stage sampling procedure. Data were analyzed using frequency, mean, food security index and logit regression model. About 22.22% of the rice farming households were food insecure. The coefficient of age, rise in prices of food, farming experience and frequency of rainfall had effects on the food security status of the rice farming households. Based on these findings, climate change has significant effect on the food security status of rice farming households in the study area. Therefore, policy interventions by government and relevant agricultural stakeholders are pertinent to scale up the use of adaptation strategies against the effects of climate change on food security status of the rice farming households in the study area.

Keywords: climate change, food security, rice, farming households

INTRODUCTION

Climate change refers to any variation in climate over time, whether due to natural variability or because of human activity (Adedeji, Tiku, Waziri-Ugwu and Sanusi, 2017). It is perhaps the most serious environmental threat currently facing mankind world-wide. Climate change affects agriculture in several ways, one of which is its direct impact on food production. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change has projected that will be increased in temperature by end of the century is likely to be in the range 1.80C to 4.00C (Manjeet and Joginder, 2018). It has been observed that in the 21st century, global warming would be more intense in many parts of the world, especially Africa, the Caribbean and parts of South-East Asia largely due to their inability to

cope. Africa is the world's most vulnerable region regarding the effects of climate change due to the fragility of economies.

Climate change is now a serious threat to Nigeria agricultural sector and food security, because of its sensitivity and susceptibility to high temperature and rainfall fluctuations (Nte and Okoro, 2017). It has adversely affected the output and yield of agricultural commodities and this poses a serious threat to the realization of food self-sufficiency drive of the Government Abu, Okpe, and Abah (2018); rising temperature and unpredictable rainfall have been found to create significant consequences in crop and livestock production as well as threatened food security.

For the past twenty years, issues relating to food security have constituted a major focus of the policy thrust of the international

community. As a matter of fact, it formed part of the major goals, which the world leaders initially agreed to devote resources to actualizing by 2015 but now by 2030 (Nwozor, Olarewaju and Ake, 2019). Food security entails ensuring sustainable access, availability and affordability of adequate quantity and quality food to all citizens.

Achieving food security remains challenging in many rural areas of Sub-Saharan Africa (FAO, 2017, Noelle *et al.*, 2018). Explicitly, the four dimensions of food security include: food availability; stability of food supplies; access to food; and food utilization. These dimensions of food security status are likely to be affected by climate change. More so, there is a direct link between climatic changes and global food insecurity more so in developing countries where climate change compounded with poverty has exacerbated the impacts. To address the challenges posed by climate change, it is necessary to examine the factors contributing to climate change and how such influence food production globally. Climatic factors like precipitation, evaporation, humidity and sunshine duration form the basis for improvement of food security.

One of the major problem facing agricultural development in Nigeria is inadequate provision of food supply to meet the requirement for the timing population. Food security is dependent on climate change variations which reduces crop yields and the land suitable for agricultural production with the greatest impacts in northern Nigeria where the greatest food security challenges persist. Therefore, food security is achieved if adequate food (quantity, quality safety, socio-cultural acceptability) is available and accessible for and satisfactorily used and utilizes by all individuals at all times to live a healthy and active life (Ezeh, Ogbo, Mbah, Diele and Iwu, 2020).

The impact of climate change on both production and food security status of rice farmers in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. Climate change had adverse effect by altering the food security status of their households thereby contributing to food inadequacy. There

has been little research on the effects of the forms of climate change on the food security status of the rice farming households in the study area. Hence, it became imperative to study the effect of climate change on the food security status of rice farming households in Kebbi State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study determined the food security status of the rice farming households and the effects of the forms of climate change on their food security status.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in Kebbi State in North West Nigeria. The State covers an estimated land area of 37,697 square kilometers. The State lies within two ecological zones: Northern part which constitutes the Sudan Savannah and the Southern part that forms the Northern Guinea Savannah. These ecological zones favour diverse agricultural production opportunities of a wide range of arable crops and livestock production. The major agricultural production activities in which the State has comparative advantage include rice, onion, yam, sorghum, vegetables, maize, cattle, camel, donkey and goat rearing and fishing.

Multi-stage sampling technique of three stage sampling procedure was used to select the households for the study. The first stage was a purposive selection of one local government area (LGA) from each agricultural zone to obtain a total of three LGAs. The purpose of this selection was due to the predominance of rice production in the LGAs. The second stage was purposive selection of five villages from each of the three LGAs due to annual cases of flood and drought in addition to predominance cultivation of rice to get a total of 15 villages for this research work. The third stage involved proportional selection of 10% from sampling frame of one thousand eight hundred and one (1801) to give a total selection of 180 rice farming households.

Table 1: Sample Frame

Agricultural zones	LGAs	Villages	Population	Sample Size
Central	Bunza	Zogirma	120	12
		Rahah	101	10
		Maidahini	119	12
		Gwade	139	14
		Salwai	141	14
Southern	Zuru	Dongo	128	13
		Koga	101	10
		Rikoto	110	11
		Kobo	100	10
		Zagdari	122	12
Northern	Argungu	T/Agoda	122	12
		Fadisanko	139	14
		Shaharma	150	15
		Dankal	99	10
		Kwararo	110	11
		Sub-total	1801	180

Source: Kebbi State ADP, 2020.

Data for this study was collected using structured questionnaire and interview schedules. Data were analysed using frequencies, percentages, mean and logit regression.

Measurement of Variables

The dependent variable of the study was food security status of rice farming households. The food security index was used to determine the food security status of each rice farming households based on the food security line using recommended daily calorie required approach.

$$\text{Food security index (K)} = \frac{\text{Household daily per capita calorie consumed (X)}}{\text{Household daily per capita calorie required (Y)}}$$

For a household to be food secure, K must be greater than or equal to 1 ($K \geq 1$). If K is less than 1 ($K < 1$), the household is food insecure. Food recall consumption method was undertaken for each of the respondent and analyse each type of food mentioned for calorie content. The quantity of food consumed was converted first to gram and further to calorie and was divided by the household size and by 7 days to obtain the calorie consumed per day per household. The result was then compared with the required standard (2260 Kcal) respectively to determine the rice farm household's food security status.

The independent variables of this study include the following:

- i. Age (year)
- ii. Rising in food prices (yes=1, otherwise=0)
- iii. Incidence of drought (number during the previous cropping season)
- iv. Farming experience (year)
- v. Educational level (year)
- vi. Farm size (hectare)
- vii. Frequency of rainfall (number of rain in the previous year)
- viii. Annual income (naira)

Based on the household food security index, the Logit regression model was estimated to determine the effects of climate change on

$$K_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + U_i$$

food security status using the rice farming households. The Logit regression model is specified as;

$$K_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_7 X_7 + \beta_8 X_8 + U_i$$

Where in the case of food security status:

K_i = Food security status ith rice farming household (1 = food secure, 0 = food insecure)

X_1 = Age (year)

X_2 = Rising in food prices (yes=1, otherwise=0)

X_3 = Incidence of drought (number of days during the previous cropping season)

X_4 = Farming experience (year)

X_5 = Educational level (year)

X_6 = Farm size (hectare)

X_7 = Frequency of rainfall (number of rain in the previous year)

X_8 = Annual income (naira)

U_i = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Rice Farming Household

Table 2 shows that majority (90.0%) of the rice farming household heads were males, a manifestation of male dominance in rice production in the study area. This is consistent with the findings of Ajibola, and Fatoki (2017) who found that majority of rice farmers were males in Niger State, Nigeria. The average age of the sampled rice farming household heads was 37 years. This implies that majority of the sampled rice household heads were within the active productive ages and energetic farmers that were receptive to innovations thereby improving their productivity. The average household size was 7 persons. This indicates that rice households in the study area have considerable large families. Previous study had shown that within the farming population, household size plays an important role in determining family labour (Dembele, Akinbile and Aminu, 2019). Likewise, the average rice farming experience of the farming households in the area was 28 years. This means that the households had long years

of rice farming experience. The rice farming households with more years of farming experience are likely to have better knowledge of the climate change variations that will help manage their food security status.

The findings from Table 2 further reveals that 43.3% of the rice farming household heads were not educated. According to Ajibola (2017), the literacy status of farmers affects the level of awareness and adoption of agricultural innovations. The average farm size of the rice farming households in the study area was 1.97 hectares which implies that majority of the respondents were small-scale farmers. This result shows that in the study area, farmland is still relatively small and therefore can be a limiting factor towards combating the effect of climate change on food security because relatively large farm size has been observed to help mitigate the effect of climate change. This agrees with Idoma, Ikpe, Ejeh, and Mamman (2017) that Nigerian farmers are small-scale farmers that cultivated small areas of land.

Table 2: Characteristics of rice farming households

Characteristics	Percentage (n=180)	Mean
Sex		
Male	90.0	
Female	10.0	
Age (years)		
=20	2.8	36.6
21-30	40.0	
31-40	27.2	
41-50	12.8	
51-60	12.2	
=60	5.0	
Household size	85.6	
1-5	32.2	8.4
6-10	37.2	
11-15	22.8	
16-20	5.6	
=21	2.2	
Rice farming experience		
1-5	17.2	27.8
6-10	27.8	
11-15	16.6	
16-20	11.7	
21-25	9.8	
25-30	7.8	
=31	10.0	
Educational level		
Primary	25.6	4.7
Secondary	19.4	
Tertiary	6.1	
No formal	43.3	
Other (Quranic)	5.6	
Farm size (ha)		
0.001-0.50	8.9	1.97
0.51-1.00	16.7	
1.01-1.50	2.8	
1.51-2.00	14.4	
2.01-2.50	0.0	
=2.51	57.2	

Source: Field survey, 2020

Food Security Status of Rice Farming Households

The result in Table 3 indicates that about 77.8% of the rice farming households were food secure while 22.2% were food insecure accordingly. The implication of this result is

that, more than average number of the rice farmers fall within and above the daily calorie consumption requirements of food security status. This connotes that despite the vagaries of climate change effects in the study area, majority of the rice farmers were food secure.

Table 3: Food security status of rice farming households

Status	Percentage (n= 180)
Food Secure	77.78
Food Insecure	22.22

Source: Field survey, 2020

Food Security Index

Table 4 shows that the weighted mean of daily food calorie consumption for food secure households and food security index was 2628.68 kcal, as the weighted mean for their daily food calorie consumption while the food security index showed (\bar{x} =1.16). Based on the recommended daily calorie intake of 2260 kcal, the average food secure households in Kebbi State had 368.68 kcal more than the

recommended daily intake in the study area. The results collaborate the findings of Haddab, Ndehfru, and Aliyu (2019) who observed that majority of the households in Mubi North local government area of Adamawa State, Nigeria were food secure but runs contrary to the findings Akukwe (2020) where majority of households in agrarian communities of south-eastern Nigeria were food insecure.

Table 4: Rice farmers according to their food security index

Variable	Mean	S. D	Min.	Max.
Food Calorie consumed	2628.68	675.62	986.87	4956.21
Food security index	1.16	0.30	0.44	2.19

Source: Field survey, 2020

Effects of Climate Change on Food Security Status of Rice Farmers

Table 5 shows that age was negatively significant at 1% level of probability. This implies that as farmers increases in age, their food security status decreases. This finding is in agreement with that of Makinta, Shetima, Ali, and Gulak (2016) that age negatively affect the food security status of farming households in Borno State. Table 5 reveals that rising in food prices was positively significant at 1% level of probability, indicating that as prices of food security of the household is expected to be affected. Also, farming experience was positively significant at 1% level of probability, showing that a unit

increase in farming experience will result to increase in food security. This might be to additional knowledge gathered over many years. Also, highly experienced farmers are expected to have adequate knowledge that will reduce the effect of climate change thereby increasing food security. Table 5 reveals that the coefficient of frequency of rainfall was positively significant at 1% level of probability. This shows that increase in rainfall with increase the food security. This result corresponds with that of Makinta *et al.* (2016) who stated that frequency of rainfall positively influences food security in Borno State.

Table 5: Effects of climate change on food security status of rice farmers

Variables	Coefficient	Z-value
Age	-0.0858765	-1.89**
Rising in food price	0.1207556	2.65***
Incidence of drought	0.1377942	0.17
Farming experience	0.1611943	3.11***
Education	0.0456312	1.00
Farm size	0.1727086	1.01
Frequency of rainfall	2.39098	3.09***
Annual income	-4.83e-08	-0.13
Constant	0.4363249	0.19
LR Chi2	43.81***	
Pseudo R2	0.4511	
Log likelihood	-65.322396	

Source: Field survey, 2020

*** Significant at 1% level of probability,

**=Significant at 5% level of probability

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was observed that age, rise in prices of food, farming experience and frequency of rainfall had effect on the food security status of the rice farming households. There is therefore need for public and private actors in the agricultural sector to be actively involved in creating awareness, enlightenment and education on best adaptation strategies rice farming households could adopt to minimize the risks

associated with the effect climate change on rice production. Efforts should also be made by research institutes, climate change institutions and relevant agricultural bodies for improved and increased innovation on climate change issues by providing more sustainable information and strategies that will help manage the effects of climate change on the food security status of rice farming households at their respective geographical local levels.

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